

Surface Water Quality in Orchard Area, Amphawa District, Samut Songkram Province, Thailand

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Abstract : This study aimed to evaluate the surface water quality for agriculture and consumption in the district. Surface water quality parameters in this study include water temperature, turbidity, conductivity, salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen, BOD, nitrate, Suspended solids, phosphorus, Total dissolved solids, iron, copper, zinc, manganese, lead and cadmium. Water samples were collected from small excavation, Lychee, Pomelo, and Coconut orchard for 3 seasons during January to December 2011. The surface water quality from small excavation, Lychee, pomelo, and coconut orchard meets the type III of surface water quality standard issued by the National Environmental Quality Act B. E. 1992, except for the concentration of heavy metals. It did not differ significantly at 0.05 level, except for dissolved oxygen. The water is suitable for consumption by the usual sterile and generally improving water quality through the process before. It is suitable for agriculture.

Keywords : water quality, surface water quality, Thailand, water

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